

Unilin panels

Furniture boards produced from recovered wood

Post-consumer wood from urban areas is collected, cleaned and processed in high tech recycling plants to re-convert into viable raw material for quality board products for furniture and interior use.

Highlights of innovative features

- Large investments in high tech sorting and cleaning equipment enables the processing of huge volumes of demolition and urban waste: up to 1 million tons are recycled into panels per year.
- Chipboards are produced with up to 90% recycled wood.
- To offset carbon emissions, factories are powered 70-90% by renewable energy from wood waste that cannot be recycled.
- Partnerships with a large supplier network including container parks, demolition firms, packaging and furniture industries ensure the recovery of large wood volumes that are no longer usable for other processes.

UNILIN represents one of the most advanced recycling systems for valorizing post-consumer wood waste streams on large industrial scale. It relies on an established collection system and supplier network. Cascading wood reduces the need for fresh roundwood and prolongs the carbon capture. Particle boards from recovered wood are a prime case for Circular Economy in the sector.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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UNILIN Panels
Ingelmunstersteenweg 229
B-8780 Oostrozebeke, Belgium

unilinpanels.com

